

DEVELOPMENT OF HOME DÉCOR FROM TEXTILE WASTE

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted at Bokod, Benguet, in 2025 with the aim of designing and creating varied home décor using textile waste utilizing exploratory sequential research design. In this study, it was found that all variations of curtain tieback, valance curtains and throw pillowcases were highly acceptable in terms of design, cultural relevance and price because the colors used are in harmony, the use of Job's tears depict natural beauty, they depict the cultural heritage of the Ibaloys and the price is affordable. Further, it surfaced that age groups 18-24 & 25-44 prefer curtain tieback, valance curtain and throw pillowcase decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads. These choices might be associated with the tendency of the 18-24-year-olds to prioritize image and trends, while 25-44-year-olds are rational when comparing and focus on long-term values. Conversely, age group 45-65 prefer curtain tieback, valance curtain and throw pillowcase decorated with pure Job's tears which might be associated with the tendencies of this age toward prioritizing convenience and simplicity. Considering that all the variations of the repurposed curtain tieback, valance curtain and throw pillowcases are highly accepted, commercialization is recommended considering the preference of each age group. Advocacy in repurposing is also recommended.

Keywords: *curtain tieback, valance curtain, throw pillowcase, cultural relevance, home décor, Job's tears, wooden beads*

INTRODUCTION

Global data on waste generation index and recycling in solid waste for 2025 showed that the top three countries with responsible waste generation and best recycling

processes are Japan, South Korea and Estonia while the top worst countries on waste generation and recycling practices are Israel, Chile and United States (Filipenco, 2025). These global data on wastes index on solid wastes for 2025, showed that few countries recycle or repurpose solid wastes. Although the Philippines was not mentioned as one of the worst, it is known that the Philippines generates 14.6 million tons of municipal solid wastes (Dela Peña, 2025). Among the solid wastes are the textile wastes which are generated from the garment factories, dressmaking shops, educational institutions and from used clothing (Phung & Nguyen, 2020).

Further, the Philippine Textile Research Institute affirms that the Philippines generates about 267,711 tons of textile wastes annually (THEPHILBIZNEWS, 2025). It was also found that textile wastes from the Philippine manufacturing and post-production processes significantly contribute to environmental degradation and resource depletion (Realino, 2025). These findings showed that reusing or re-purposing textile wastes needs to be strengthened through advocacy supported with product development that generates income.

Several studies (Uddin, 2025; Mei, et al., 2025; Abrishami, et al., 2024) examined recycling and reusing. However, the results of these studies are only feasible in developed countries that developing countries such as the Philippines can't afford because the technologies discovered are highly technical. Further, the discovered processes of reusing and recycling involve the use of chemicals in which these procedures differ from the current study for the processes used focused on re-purposing with integration of ethnic designs. Moreover, the textile wastes used in the current study are pre-consumer textile waste comprising the biodegradable materials primarily fabric scraps. Likewise, this study focuses on turning pre-consumer textile wastes specifically fabric scraps into home decor products to help reduce the quantity of textile waste being burned or thrown in landfills.

Previous studies have demonstrated ways to repurpose textile waste into fashion items (Anil et al., 2022) and into home and interior decorations (Kushwana & Swami, 2016; Sai et al., 2022; Pramono et al., 2022; Alimin et al., 2022; Abdulkadir et al., 2023), however, only few of these studies (Kushwana & Swami, 2016; Abdulkadir et al., 2023) have evaluated the acceptability of the products. Moreover, the studies failed to evaluate the cultural relevance and price acceptability which are important in determining the market potential of the developed products.

While some studies (Pramono et. al, 2022; Guo & Li, 2023) demonstrated the integration of cultural concepts and natural elements in creating textile-based home décor items, there were no studies that explored the integration of job tears into the designs of curtain tieback, valance curtain, and throw pillowcase. Similarly, there were no studies found focused on describing the level of acceptability of repurposed curtain tieback, valance curtain, and throw pillowcase decorated with Job's tears; the cultural relevance of the Job's tears as embellishment as well as the acceptability of price of each repurposed item. The absence of such studies presents an opportunity to come up with eco-friendly home décor products out of textile wastes decorated with Job's tears that

provide economic opportunity and further contribute to the achievement of sustainable development goal number 12 which refers to responsible consumption and production.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to design and create varied home décor using textile waste.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the textile waste disposal practices of technical vocational schools offering clothing or garment technology and dressmakers at Bokod, Benguet and the challenges they met in repurposing their textile wastes?
2. What is the level of the acceptability of the repurposed home décor products in terms of:
 - 2.1. Design
 - 2.2. Cultural relevance
 - 2.3. Price
3. What is the most preferred repurposed product variation by comparing the aggregated acceptability rating of products in terms of design, cultural relevance and pricing among the age groups?
 - 3.1. 18-24 years old
 - 3.2. 25-44 years old
 - 3.3. 45-65 years old; and
4. What are the procedures in repurposing textile wastes into curtain tieback, valance and throw pillowcase?

METHODOLOGY

The study used an exploratory sequential design. In this design, three stages were carried out. For stage 1 (Research Question 1), four teachers, four students, and two sewing practitioners were interviewed on the disposal practices of the textile wastes generated from their classrooms or dressmaking shops, and the challenges met in repurposing the textile wastes. In stage 2 (Research Question 2), curtain tiebacks, valance curtains, and throw pillowcases were constructed in three variations, which comprise the following: A) Variation 1. Product decorated with pure Job's tears; B) Variation 2. Product decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads; and C) Variation 3. Product decorated with Job's tears mixed with commercial plastic beads.

Procedural analysis (Liu et al., 2023) was simultaneously done with the construction of curtain tiebacks, valance curtains, and throw pillowcases. This was done to explore systematic and detailed procedures. For the construction of first variations of curtain tiebacks, valance curtains, and throw pillowcases, existing procedures were used (Beck, 2021; Kwik-Hang, 2020; Laura, 2025; Mulvenna, 2020).

Based on the procedures executed in the first variations, procedural analysis was executed by three experts in sewing, wherein data on total operation time and speed time were calculated. After which, weaknesses of the procedures were identified, and improvements were listed by the researcher. Based on the listed improvements on the procedures in variation 1, the second variation of curtain tiebacks, valance curtains, and throw pillowcases were constructed. The data on the operation time, speed time, and material handling movement were analyzed by three sewing experts and listed suggested improvements which were considered in constructing the third variations of curtain tiebacks, valance curtains, and throw pillowcases.

After the construction of the three variations of curtain tiebacks, valance curtains, and throw pillowcases, they were presented to adult community members for acceptability evaluation in terms of design, cultural significance, and price.

Population and Locale of the Study

The respondents were selected using purposive sampling. Teachers teaching TVL (Garment technology) from educational institutions in Bokod and dressmakers or tailors from Bokod, Benguet who are directly involved with dressmaking or tailoring were selected as respondents for the study. Likewise, students in dressmaking from the educational institutions in Bokod were also involved.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

Classification of Respondents	Total Number	Percentage
Teachers	4	5.97%
Students	4	5.97%
Sewing practitioners	2	2.96%
Adult community members	57	85.1%
Total	67	100%

As shown in Table 1, there were four teachers (5.97%), four students (5.97%) and two sewing practitioners (2.96%) were interviewed regarding the modes of textile waste disposal they practiced and the challenges they encountered in repurposing. These teachers and students came from educational institutions in Bokod. The two sewing practitioners were engaged in dressmaking and tailoring, regardless of whether they were the owners or sewers, as there are only two sewing practitioners in the locality. In the acceptability assessment, 57 respondents, comprising 85.1% were involved. Purposive selection was done from target end users aged 18 to 65 who had knowledge on the use and meaning of Job's tears; and possessed basic sewing skills. The 57 respondents who were involved in the acceptability survey were equally distributed in three age groups with the following distribution: a) group 1: 18-24, b) age group 2: 25-44, and c) group 3: 45-65 years old. This age range encompasses a diverse group of consumers who encompass differences in product acceptance. For instance, Liu (2024),

in his article highlighted major distinctions in product acceptance across age groups: individuals aged 18-24 prioritize image and trends; those aged 25-44 years emphasize long-term value and rational comparisons; and those aged 45-60 years prefer convenient products, reliable brands, which are affected by economic and technology acceptance.

In assessing the acceptability of the home décor products, the background knowledge in the use of Job's tears, and basic sewing skills were considered in the selection. Community members aged 17 and below were excluded in the study.

Data Collection Instruments

In the conduct of the study, the researcher used the following data collection instruments to ensure that the necessary data were collected.

For Research Question 1, interview guide was used. The interview guide was structured to follow a logical flow, starting with an introduction, moving into the main discussion topics, and concluding with an opportunity for the participant to provide additional insights. It comprised of open-ended questions focused on the actual utilization of textile waste materials. Finally, the interview guide captured the respondents' suggestions in the utilization of textile waste.

For Research Question 2 and 3, an adapted-modified acceptability survey questionnaire was developed and tested for content validity among three experts where the computed content validity index was 1.0. The questionnaire used a 5 Likert scale with 5.0-4.21 as strongly agree, 4.20-3.41 as agree, 3.4-2.61 as neutral and, 2.60-1.81 as disagree. Respondents were asked to evaluate the created home decor using three criteria which includes design, cultural relevance and price acceptability basing on three acceptability statements. For the design and pricing criteria, the statements were adapted and modified from the studies of Amubode (2005) while the statements for cultural relevance were adapted and modified from Adedotun et al. (2015).

For Research Question 4, an observation guide was used to document the total operation time, stitching speed, and material handling movement.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection procedure in this study involved a combination of interviews, observations, product development and survey.

The process on data collection begun by preparing and sending introductory letters to the Municipal Mayor of Bokod and to the school heads of the aforementioned participating schools introducing the research objectives, and requesting their cooperation and support. The researcher then visited the target respondents in their respective locations. During these visits, the researcher explained to the respondents the purpose of the study and asked if they are willing to participate in the research. After signing the informed consent, the respondents were observed and interviewed to

document current practices and processes related to textile waste utilization. The researcher also asked permission to some of the respondents if they could provide discarded textile waste to be used in the product development.

The researcher started the product development and documented the steps involved in the product development process through written documentation and kept the patterns used in the study, including the notes of the procedures followed in making the home décor products.

To assess the acceptability of the developed home décor products, the researcher conducted a product evaluation survey using an adapted modified acceptability questionnaire. One questionnaire was provided for every respondent who was willing to participate. These were used to gather feedback from consumers representing different age groups on the design, cultural relevance, and pricing of the products.

To ensure effective communication and feedback throughout the study, the researcher began by mapping out the possible groups of respondents who would participate in the study. This involved identifying and locating schools, students, teachers, individuals, and businesses offering sewing and clothing alteration services, and members of the local community, before developing the interview and observation guide to determine the suitable level and method of engagement for each group.

After developing the interview and observation guide, the researcher gathered detailed information from the willing respondents through interviews and observation, which allowed the researcher to learn more about the existing practices in the schools and industry setting and use them as an example for designing and developing home décor products. The product development phase started by gathering the necessary materials, sewing tools, and equipment to create the home decor products. The preparation of materials specifically the textile waste involved washing, and sorting while Job's tears preparation involved gathering the seeds, drying, and removing of its debris to speed up threading. In the design process, watching Youtube tutorials on how beads can be attached to fabric was done. The researcher then proceeded with the implementation and construction of the home decor products.

Then, the content validation of the adapted-modified acceptability questionnaire was conducted to ensure its content validity in which it was rated as 4 or highly valid, with two statements classified as vague, but were revised before administering the survey questionnaire. The instrument was used to measure the three acceptability aspects, such as the design, cultural relevance, and pricing.

Treatment of Data

The responses from the participants during the interview and product evaluation were analyzed using the following methods.

For Research Question 1, thematic analysis was used to identify common themes and insights on the utilization of textile wastes in TVL classes and dressmaking and tailoring shops. The thematic process proposed by Braun & Clarke (2019) was followed in this study, which comprises the steps of familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes; and finally reporting or interpreting.

For Research Question 2 and 3, descriptive statistics, specifically the mean, were utilized. The mean for each criterion statement was computed before it was averaged. The following table was used in interpreting the data in terms of acceptability of design.

Table 2. Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) for Acceptability of Home Decor in Terms Design

Mean Range	Numerical Equivalent	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
4.21-5.00	5	Strongly agree	All color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate. All aspects of design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of job's tears and complements the overall design. All aspects of the design of the home décor are well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.
3.41-4.20	4	Agree	Most color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate. Most aspects of the design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of Job's tears and complements the overall design. Most aspects of design of the home décor are well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.
2.61- 3.40	3	Neutral	More color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate. More aspects of the design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of Job's tears and complements the overall design. More aspects of design of the home décor are well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.
1.81- 2.60	2	Disagree	Few color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate. Few aspects of the design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of Job's tears and complements the overall design. Few aspects of design of the home décor are well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.
1.0- 1.80	1	Strongly Disagree	One color combination used is harmonious and appropriate.one aspect of the design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of job's

tears and complements the overall design. one aspect of design of the home décor is well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.

The next table was used to interpret the data gathered on the acceptability of the constructed curtain tiebacks, valance curtain and throw pillowcases in terms of cultural relevance.

Table 3. Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) for Acceptability of Curtain Tiebacks, Valance Curtain and Throw Pillowcases in Terms of Cultural Relevance

Mean Range	Numerical Equivalent	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
4.21-5.00	5	Strongly agree	The use of Job's tears in the home décor excellently aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy. It excellently resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way and excellently promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods.
3.41-4.20	4	Agree	The use of job's tears in the home décor is outstandingly aligned with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy. It outstandingly resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way. It outstandingly promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods
2.61- 3.40	3	Neutral	The use of Job's tears in the home décor is somewhat aligned with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy. It somewhat resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way. It somewhat promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods.
1.81- 2.60	2	Disagree	The use of Job's tears in the home décor is partially aligned with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy. It partially resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way. It partially promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods
1.0- 1.80	1	Strongly Disagree	The use of Job's tears in the home décor is poorly Disagree aligned with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy. It poorly resonates with the local

community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way. It poorly promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods.

The following table was used to interpret the acceptability of the constructed curtain tiebacks, valance curtain, and throw pillowcases in terms of cultural relevance.

Table 4. Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) for Acceptability of Home Decor in Terms of Pricing Acceptability

Mean Range	Numerical Equivalent	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
4.21-5.00	5	Strongly Agree	The price of the home décor is highly acceptable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.
3.41-4.20	4	Agree	The price of the home décor is reasonably acceptable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.
2.61-3.40	3	Neutral	The price of the home décor is somewhat acceptable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.
1.81-2.60-	2	Disagree	The price of the home décor is least acceptable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.
1.0-1.80	1	Strongly Disagree	The price of the home décor is never acceptable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.

For Research Question 4, procedural analysis (Li et al., 2023) was executed. Collected data on sewing speed time, and operation time when using existing procedures, and the researcher’s modified sewing procedures for curtain tieback, valance, and throw pillowcase were calculated and compared the difference. Calculating speed time in sewing followed the formula (Sarkar, 2019): sewing time (in seconds) = stitches required for seam X 60 divide by Machine revolution per minute.

In calculating the operation time, the following formula was used: Basic Time = Observed Time × (Operator Rating Factor / 100). Basic time accounts for the operator's performance speed relative to a standard pace. Then compute the Standard Time using the formula (Mondal, et al.,2024): (SMV) = Basic Time × (1 +

Allowance Percentage). Standard time incorporates necessary allowances into the basic time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mode of Textile Waste Utilization in TVL classes or Dressmaking Shops (Research Question 1)

The following table presents the responses on the textile wastes disposal and repurposing practices at the TVL educational institutions and dressmaking shops at Bokod, Benguet.

Table 5. Responses on the Mode of Textile Waste Disposal

Themes	Responses
Storage/collection	Fabric scraps were put in sacks for future use and sometimes given to individuals who want to use it. Respondent 1. Boxes were provided where students put their fabric scraps. Respondent 2 Students leave their fabric scraps inside the cabinets Respondent 4
Repurposing practices	Fabric scraps are used to make potholders while some are used to make bed sheets through patching Respondent 1 Students use the fabric scraps to make foot rugs while some are integrated in their projects. Respondent 2 I make foot rugs or pin cushion from fabric scraps while some are used in our projects. especially the wide ones. Respondent 3 I require my students to make scrunchies, headband and rugs using the fabric scraps while the wide fabric scraps were kept in the cabinet for future use. Respondent 4 I make hair accessories from fabric scraps. Respondent 11 I ask my students to make rugs through quilting/patching. Respondent 5 I make foot rugs or potholders. Respondent 10 I let my students use the fabric scraps to practice the manipulation of sewing machine. While some are used to make potholders. Respondent 6 I make pin cushion using fabric scraps. Respondent 7 I use fabric scraps in patching torn jeans/clothes. Respondent 8 I use the fabric scraps to patch torn jeans/denim clothes while some are used to make seat cover. Respondent 9
Disposal of	I give them to someone who use it to make pillows.

unused/remaining fabric scraps	Respondent 1 I ask my students to bring them home. Respondent 6 I instruct my students to bring them home but some student just leave it on the cabinet. Respondent 4 I throw them in the trash can. Respondent 7 The other fabric scraps were asked by my colleagues to be used to wipe windows and for applying floor wax. Respondent 5
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Table 5 shows the themes generated from the responses of the respondents from TVL dressmaking/tailoring classes and dressmaking shops at Bokod, Benguet:

Storage/collection

In this study, storage and collection refers to how textile wastes generated from dressmaking shops and schools offering dressmaking/tailoring specializations at Bokod, Benguet are collected and kept.

Based on interviews and observations, it was found that textile wastes generated from garment construction are put on a sack or box. Some are stored in the cabinet for future use. These forms of collection and storage were affirmed by respondent number 1 who stated that textile wastes generated from garment construction in a dressmaking shop are stored in a sack for future use. Similarly, respondent number 4 affirmed that textile wastes generated from projects of the students in dressmaking are kept in a box or cabinet. These data imply the need to strengthen the advocacy on Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003) in educational institutions and among dressmakers at Bokod, Benguet.

Repurposing Practices

Repurposing practices in this study denotes how textile wastes generated on garment construction are utilized to produce new products. It offers simple yet viable alternative modes of disposing textile wastes (Aus et al., 2021 & Sai et al., 2020).

Based on the interviews conducted to dressmakers, TVL teachers and students, it was known that the textile wastes generated from garment construction are used as rugs as claimed by respondents 3,4,5 & 10 as stated: "I used them as rugs", "I used them for quilted foot rugs", and "I used them for foot rugs". On the other hand, it was found that textile wastes are used as patches for seat cover or pant as claimed by respondents 1, 5, 8 & 9 by claiming: "I use them to patch pants", "I use them for seat cover". Others (respondents 11 & 4) claimed that they use the textile wastes to make hair accessories like head bands. Further, respondents 7 & 3 claimed to have used the textile wastes into pin cushion stuffing. Lastly, respondents 6 & 10 claimed to have used the them for making pot holder.

These findings demonstrated that there were efforts done in repurposing textile wastes among dressmakers and educational institutions at Bokod, Benguet, however, they were not within the context of upcycling or repurposing because upcycling involves transforming waste materials into new products of better quality or higher environmental value (Aus et al., 2021), while repurposing gives waste materials a new purpose by creating something different from the original item (Sai et al., 2020).

These findings imply the importance of strengthening of advocacy on the economic benefits from wastes through modeling and commercialization strategy.

Challenges on Repurposing Textile Wastes Among TVL Classes and Dressmaking Shops (Research Question 1)

Challenges in repurposing refer to the factors or barriers encountered in repurposing the textile wastes by the TVL teachers, students and dressmakers at Bokod, Benguet which are collected through the interview.

The following table shows the challenges met by the dressmakers, TVL students and TVL teachers of Bokod, Benguet in repurposing textile wastes.

Table 6. Challenges on Repurposing Textile Wastes Among TVL Classes and Dressmaking Shops

Themes	Responses
Challenges	The sizes of the fabric scraps are varied that it is difficult to identify what product to make. Respondent 4 Based on observation, students are not willing to repurpose, they don't value the money used for buying the cloth. Respondent 4 As much as I want to, I don't have time to repurpose because I am full load with teaching. Respondent 2 We lack manpower and time to do repurposing. Respondent 1 I don't have time to repurpose fabric scraps because of a lot of paper works that needs to be done Respondent 5 We don't have enough equipment to do repurposing. Respondent 3 I don't have time to repurpose. Respondent 6

Table 6 shows that one challenge for not repurposing textile wastes generated from TVL classes and dressmaking shops at Bokod, Benguet is irregular shapes of the wastes. It was affirmed that the sizes of the textile wastes are varied, as respondent number 4 said: "the sizes of the fabric scraps are varied making it difficult to identify what product to make". Another factor is time constraint, which is confirmed with the statement of respondent number 2: "As much as I want to, I don't have time to repurpose because I have a full teaching load"; respondent number 5 & 6: "I don't have enough time to repurpose due to lots of paperwork".

These data suggest that the most prevalent challenges in repurposing textile wastes for dressmakers, TVL teachers and students at Bokod, Benguet are time constraints followed by the textile wastes shapes which is similar to the findings in a study conducted by Yusuff (2024) where one identified challenge in recycling textile wastes is heterogeneity of materials.

Assessment of Curtain Tiebacks, Valance Curtain and Throw Pillowcase in Terms of Design, Cultural Relevance and Price (Research Question 2)

Assessment of Curtain Tieback in Terms of Design (Research Question 2.1)

Table 7.1 Acceptability of Curtain Tiebacks in Terms of Design

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1 (with pure Job's tears embellishment)		Variation 2 (with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		Variation 3 (with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate.	4.18	Agree	4.33	Strongly agree	4.18	Agree
2. The design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of Job's tears and complements the overall design.	4.44	Strongly Agree	4.42	Strongly agree	4.18	Agree
3. The design of the home décor is well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.	4.4	Strongly Agree	4.35	Strongly agree	4.21	Strongly Agree
Average	4.34	Strongly Agree	4.37	Strongly agree	4.19	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

For the acceptability of design, Table 7 shows that the curtain tieback accentuated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads was rated strongly agree in terms of design (\bar{x} = 4.37), while the curtain tieback accentuated with Job's tears mixed with plastic beads was rated agree (\bar{x} = 4.19). These findings indicate that curtain tiebacks accentuated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads were highly accepted in terms of design due to the observations that all the color combinations used were harmonious and appropriate. All aspects of design of the curtain tiebacks showcase the natural beauty of Job's tears and

complements the overall design and all aspects of the design of the curtain tieback is well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements. These findings are consistent with the findings of Pramono et al. (2022), which demonstrated that integrating Islamic motifs in upcycling textile wastes results to highly accepted repurposed products.

Assessment of Curtain Tieback in Terms of Cultural Relevance (Research Question 2.2)

Table 7.2 Acceptability of Curtain Tiebacks in Terms of Cultural Relevance

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1 (with pure Job's tears embellishment)		Variation 2 (with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		Variation 3 (with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The use of Job's tears in the home décor aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy.	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.68	Strongly Agree	4.14	Agree
2. The design of the home décor resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way.	4.49	Strongly Agree	4.44	Strongly Agree	4.14	Agree
3. The home décor promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods.	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.32	Strongly Agree
Average	4.46	Strongly agree	4.55	Strongly agree	4.2	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

Table 7.2 shows that the curtain tieback embellished with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.55) in terms of cultural significance, while curtain tie back with Job's tears mixed with plastic beads was agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.2). These findings indicate that the use of Job's tears in the curtain tieback excellently aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy. The design excellently resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way, and promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture while supporting local traditions and livelihoods.

Assessment of Curtain Tieback in Terms of Price (Research Question 2.3)

Table 7. 3 Acceptability of Curtain Tiebacks in Terms of Price

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1		Variation 2		Variation 3	
	(with pure Job's tears embellishment)		(with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		(with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The price of the home décor is reasonable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.	4.44	Strongly Agree	4.49	Strongly Agree	4.37	Strongly Agree
The price of the home decor is affordable for the amount of 49	4.54	Strongly Agree	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.42	Strongly Agree
The price of the home decor is competitive compared to similar products on the market.	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.35	Strongly Agree
Average	4.5	Strongly Agree	4.5	Strongly Agree	4.38	Strongly Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

Table 7.3 shows that the Php 49 price of the curtain tieback decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads and decorated with pure Job's tears was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.5) in terms of price. Further, it was found that a curtain tieback decorated with Job's tears mixed with plastic beads beads was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.38) in terms of price.

These findings indicate that the Php 49 price of the curtain tieback is highly acceptable, considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production. It also suggests that the price is perceived as affordable and competitive. These findings are supported by the principle of "austerity" (Keinzler et al.,2017) stating that price of products enhances the acceptability of the product.

In summary, the curtain tieback decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads was the most highly accepted variation in terms of design, cultural relevance, and price based on average mean (\bar{x} = 4.47). The high acceptability is influenced by the

following observations: a) color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate; b) all aspects of design of the curtain tie backs showcase the natural beauty of Job's tears and complements the overall design; c) all aspects of the design of the curtain tieback is well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements; d) use of Job's tears in the curtain tieback excellently aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy; e) excellently resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way; f) excellently promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods; and g) price is affordable and competitive considering the craftsmanship put into it.

Assessment of Valance Curtain in Terms of Design (Research Question 2.1)

Table 8.1 Acceptability of Valance Curtain in terms of Design

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1 (with pure Job's tears embellishment)		Variation 2 (with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		Variation 3 (with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate.	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.68	Strongly Agree	4.14	Agree
2. The design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of Job's tears and complements the overall design.	4.49	Strongly Agree	4.44	Strongly Agree	4.14	Agree
3. The design of the home décor is well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.32	Strongly Agree
Average	4.46	Strongly Agree	4.55	Strongly Agree	4.2	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

As shown in Table 8.1, valance curtain accentuated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads was strongly agreed upon in terms of design (\bar{x} = 4.55), while valance curtain embellished with Job’s tears mixed with plastic beads was agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.2).

The findings surfaced the assumption that all color combinations used in the valance curtain accentuated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads are harmonious and appropriate. All aspects of design of the valance showcase the natural beauty of Job’s tears and complement the overall design and all aspects of the design of the valance is well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements. Previous studies (Abdulkadir et al., 2023, Alimin et al., 2022, Anil et al., 2022, Pramono et al., 2022, and Sai et al., 2022) support these findings.

Assessment of Valance Curtain in Terms of Cultural Relevance (Research Question 2.2)

Table 8.2 Acceptability of Valance Curtain in Terms of Cultural Significance

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1 (with pure Job’s tears embellishment)		Variation 2 (with Job’s tears & wooden beads embellishment)		Variation 3 (with Job’s tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The use of Job's tears in the home décor aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy.	4.49	Strongly Agree	4.47	Strongly Agree	4.21	Strongly Agree
2. The design of the home décor resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way.	4.46	Strongly Agree	4.54	Strongly Agree	4.18	Agree
3. The home décor promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods.	4.54	Strongly Agree	4.54	Strongly Agree	4.23	Strongly Agree
Average	4.5	Strongly Agree	4.52	Strongly Agree	4.2	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

The table shows that valance curtain decorated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.52) while valance curtain decorated with

Job's tears mixed with plastic beads was agreed (\bar{x} = 4.2) in terms of cultural significance. These data imply that valance curtain decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads was highly accepted due to the observations that the use of Job's tears in the valance curtain excellently aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy and resonates the local community and incorporates culturally meaningful elements. These findings are supported with the theory of Material Culture by Schlanger (2020), which asserts that physical objects are linked to traditions or beliefs.

Assessment of Valance Curtain in Terms of Price (Research Question 2.3)

Table 8. 3 Acceptability of Valance Curtain in Terms of Price

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1		Variation 2		Variation 3	
	(with pure Job's tears embellishment)		(with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		(with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The price of the home décor is reasonable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.39	Strongly Agree
2. The price of the home decor is affordable for the amount of 89	4.44	Strongly Agree	4.46	Strongly Agree	4.33	Strongly Agree
3. The price of the home decor is competitive compared to similar products on the market.	4.46	Strongly Agree	4.42	Strongly Agree	4.19	Agree
Average	4.48	Strongly Agree	4.47	Strongly Agree	4.3	Strongly Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree-1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

Table 8.3 shows that the price amounting to Php 89 for valance curtain decorated with pure Job's tears was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} =4.48) in terms of price implying that 89 Php price is highly accepted. This result coincides with the findings of Cakranegara et al. (2022), who concluded that as long as the product is considered affordable by the consumers, it will receive an automatic acceptance in the community.

Assessment of Throw Pillowcase in Terms of Design (Research Question 2.1)

Table 9.1 Acceptability of Throw Pillowcase in Terms of Design

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1 (with pure Job's tears embellishment)		Variation 2 (with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		Variation 3 (with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate.	4.33	Strongly Agree	4.39	Strongly Agree	4.26	Strongly Agree
2. The design of the home décor showcases the natural beauty of Job's tears and complements the overall design.	4.42	Strongly Agree	4.33	Strongly Agree	4.16	Agree
3. The design of the home décor is well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements.	4.3	Strongly Agree	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.25	Strongly Agree
Average	4.35	Strongly Agree	4.35	Strongly Agree	4.22	Strongly Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

Table 9.1 shows that throw pillowcases embellished with pure Job's tears and throw pillowcases decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads were strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.35) in terms of design.

The data imply that all the variations were highly acceptable to the respondents. It also indicates that the design of the throw pillowcase was highly acceptable with the perception that all color combinations used are harmonious and appropriate. In addition, all aspects of design of the valance showcase the natural beauty of Job's tears and complement the overall design. Furthermore, all aspects of the design of the valance are well-suited for a wide range of styles, effectively blending traditional and modern elements which is supported by the study of Alimin et al., (2022) and Abdulkadir et al., (2023).

Assessment of Throw Pillowcase in terms of Cultural Significance (Research Question 2.2)

Table 9.2 Acceptability of Throw Pillowcase in Terms of Cultural Significance

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1 (with pure Job's tears embellishment)		Variation 2 (with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		Variation 3 (with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The use of Job's tears in the home décor aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy.	4.39	Strongly Agree	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.25	Strongly Agree
2. The design of the home décor resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way.	4.52	Strongly Agree	4.26	Strongly Agree	4.16	Agree
3. The home décor promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods.	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.26	Strongly Agree
Average	4.41	Strongly Agree	4.38	Strongly Agree	4.22	Strongly Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

As shown in Table 9.2, the throw pillowcases accentuated with pure Job's tears was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.41) in terms of cultural significance. The findings imply that the throw pillowcase was highly accepted as they possess cultural relevance. Respondents observed that the use of Job's tears in the home décor aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy, that the design of the home décor resonates with the local community and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way and that the use of Job's tears promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture.

These findings are supported by the study of Bugtong (2025) which found out that "kambayasho" (topper) was accentuated with Job's tears and acorus calamus Linn was highly accepted.

Assessment of Throw Pillowcase in Terms of Price (Research Question 2.3)

Table 9. 3 Acceptability of Throw Pillowcase in Terms of Price

Statements	Mean and Qualitative Description (QD) Per variation					
	Variation 1 (with pure Job's tears embellishment)		Variation 2 (with Job's tears & wooden beads embellishment)		Variation 3 (with Job's tears & plastic beads embellishment)	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The price of the home décor is reasonable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production.	4.32	Strongly Agree	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.25	Strongly Agree
2. The price of the home decor is affordable for the amount of 49	4.49	Strongly Agree	4.47	Strongly Agree	4.39	Strongly Agree
3. The price of the home decor is competitive compared to similar products on the market.	4.4	Strongly Agree	4.47	Strongly Agree	4.3	Agree
Average	4.4	Strongly Agree	4.44	Strongly Agree	4.32	Strongly Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

The data in table 9.3 showed that 49 pesos as price of throw pillowcase decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.44). This implies that the price amounting to 49 pesos is highly acceptable considering the materials, time, effort, and skilled craftsmanship put into its production. These results are supported by a study (Cakranegara et al., 2022) which concluded that as long as the product is considered affordable by the consumers, it will receive an automatic acceptance in the community.

Assessment of Curtain Tieback, Valance Curtain and Throw Pillowcases in Terms of Design, Cultural Relevance and Price according to Age Groups (Research Question 3)

Assessment of Curtain Tieback per Age Group in Terms of Design, Cultural Relevance, and Price (Research Question 3.1)

Table 10. 1 Acceptability of Curtain Tieback per Age Group in Terms of Design, Cultural relevance, and Price

Age Groups	Average Mean of Design, Cultural relevance and Price acceptability Per Curtain Tieback Variation		
	Curtain Tieback (decorated with pure Job's tears)	Curtain Tieback (decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads)	Curtain Tieback (decorated with Job's tears mixed with plastic beads)
18-24 years old	4.37	4.44	4.35
25-44 years old	4.34	4.41	4.25
45-65 years old	4.6	4.5	4.21

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

Based on the presented data in Table 10.1, 18-24 years old strongly prefer (\bar{x} = 4.44) curtain tieback decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden bead in terms of design, cultural relevance and price. These findings coincide with the findings of Liu (2024) that product acceptance for 18-24 years prioritize image and trends.

Likewise, 25-44 years old strongly prefer (\bar{x} = 4.41) curtain tieback decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads in terms of design, cultural relevance and price. This means that this age group strongly agree that the curtain tieback with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads exhibits harmonious color combinations, showcases natural beauty, aligned to cultural heritage, resonates local community and offers a reasonable price. These findings are supported by Liu (2024), who noted that individuals ages 25-44 tend to emphasize long-term value and rational product comparisons.

However, curtain tieback decorated with pure Job's tears was strongly preferred (\bar{x} = 4.6) by respondents aged 45-65. These data imply that the curtain tieback with pure Job's tears decoration was the most acceptable design among respondents aged 45-65. These findings relate to the concept that 45-60 years of age prefer convenient but simple products, reliable brands, and have economic advantage (Liu, 2024).

Assessment of Valance Curtain per Age Group in Terms of Design, Cultural Relevance, and Price (Research Question 3.2)

Table 10.2. Acceptability of Valance Curtain per age group in terms of Design, Cultural relevance, and Price

Age Groups	Average Mean of Design, Cultural relevance and Price Acceptability Per Valance Curtain Variation		
	Valance Curtain (decorated with pure Job's tears)	Valance Curtain (decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads)	Valance Curtain (decorated with Job's tears mixed with plastic beads)
18-24 years old	4.30	4.43	4.32

25-44 years old	4.44	4.58	4.34
45-65 years old	4.55	4.43	4.09

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

Table 10.2 shows that valance curtain decorated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads was strongly agreed upon (\bar{x} = 4.43) in terms of design, cultural relevance and price for respondents aged 18-24. These findings imply that valance curtain accentuated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads are highly accepted by age group. This is due to the observation that the colors used in the valance curtain are harmonious, the design showcases natural beauty, resonates local community, aligns with cultural heritage, and is offered at an affordable price.

Similarly, respondents aged 25-44, strongly agreed (\bar{x} = 4. 58) with the valance curtain decorated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads. These findings imply that valance curtain decorated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads was highly acceptable in terms of design, cultural relevance, and price. The result is supported by Liu (2024), which asserts that individuals aged 24-44 tend to emphasize long-term value and rational comparisons when evaluating products.

However, respondents aged 45-65 strongly agreed (\bar{x} = 4.55) with valance curtain decorated with pure Job’s tears in terms of design, cultural significance and price. These findings imply that this age group prefers home décor which aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy, resonates the local community, and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way. Furthermore, such designs promote the preservation of Ibaloy culture and support local traditions and livelihoods. These findings relate to the concept that 45-60 years of age prefer convenient but simple products, reliable brands, and have economic advantage (Liu, 2024).

Assessment of Throw Pillowcase per Age Group in Terms of Design, Cultural Relevance, and Price (Research Question 3.3)

Table 10.3. Acceptability of Throw Pillowcase per Age Group in Terms of Design, Cultural relevance, and Price

Age Groups	Average Mean of Design, Cultural relevance and Price Acceptability per Throw Pillowcase Variation		
	Throw Pillowcase (decorated with pure Job’s tears)	Throw Pillowcase (decorated with Job’s tears mixed with wooden beads)	Throw Pillowcase (decorated with Job’s tears mixed with plastic beads)
18-24 years old	4.44	4.43	4.39
25-44 years old	4.38	4.45	4.32
45-65 years old	4.39	4.38	4.09

Legend: Strongly Agree- 4.21-5.00, Agree- 3.41-4.20, Neutral- 2.61-3.40, Disagree- 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree- 1.00-1.81

The table above shows that a throw pillowcase decorated with pure Job's tears was strongly accepted (\bar{x} = 4.44) by respondents aged 18-24. These findings relate to the concept of balancing aesthetics, creativity, practicality, and quality while considering cultural factors to improve consumer acceptance, specifically of cultural and creative products (Jia et al., 2024).

Similarly, respondents aged 25-44 strongly agreed (\bar{x} = 4.45) with the throw pillowcase with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads decoration. These findings denote that the throw pillowcase decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads was highly acceptable in terms of design, cultural relevance and price. This may be attributed to the perception that the design aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy, resonates with the local community, and incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way. Furthermore, it relevantly promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture and supports local traditions and livelihoods.

Lastly, respondents aged 45-65 strongly agreed (\bar{x} = 4.39) with the throw pillowcase accentuated with pure Job's tears in terms of design, cultural relevance and price. These findings imply that the preferences of respondents aged 45-65 are similar to those of the 18-24 age group, claiming that the design excellently aligns with the cultural heritage of the Ibaloy. Moreover, the design resonates with the local community, incorporates cultural elements in a meaningful way, and promotes the preservation of Ibaloy culture while supporting local traditions and livelihoods. These findings further support the conclusions of Jia et al. (2024) stating that balancing aesthetics, creativity, practicality, and quality while considering cultural factors improves consumer acceptance specifically of cultural and creative products.

Using the procedural analysis, the following procedures in making home décor products were determined as effective (Li et al., 2023). With these procedures, the operation time decreased because material handling movements are systematic.

Procedures in Making Home Décor (Research Question 4)

Procedures in Making Curtain Tieback

The following procedures were identified for making curtain tieback in which there was 10 minutes' reduction in operation time due to systematic materials handling movements compared to existing procedures (Kwik Hang, 2020). The steps are: a) Measure 2 1/2" by 8" in the fabric providing 1/2" seam allowance in all sides. b) Cut the fabric, c) Cut 2 1/2" by 8" fusible pelon, d) Press the 2 1/2" by 8" fusible interfacing on the wrong side of one of the cuts 2 1/2"x 8" fabrics, observing the marks on the fabric to fit, e) With the right sides together, machine stitch the cut 2 1/2: x 8" fabric starting on the narrower side, leaving one wider side half open, f) Cut/trim the corners of the sewn 2 1/2 by 8 inches fabric to avoid puckering of corners. Turn it inside out. g) Fold the unstitched seam allowance towards the inside. h) Topstitch all the sides for about 1/8" from the edge,

i) Cut 2" of white Velcro tape. Locate the placement of the Velcro tape on the center side of the sewn 2 ½" x 8" fabric, then permanently stitch all the sides of the Velcro tape, j) Locate the pair of the 2" Velcro tape on the other side by folding back the tieback, k) Attach the Velcro tape by sewing permanently using straight sewing machine. For the procedures in attaching the job's tears embellishment l) First variation: embellish the sewn fabric with pure job's tears beads following the threading procedure (needle, matching thread, bead orientation). Thread a hand needle using a thread color that matches the color of the bead, m) Insert needle on the side seam. n) Thread two Job's tears coming in on the widest portion going out on the pointed portion of the Job's tears. o) For the third Job's tears, thread from the pointed part of the bead going out of the wide part. p) Insert needle for about half an inch away from the first Job's tears, then pull. q) Insert needle on the third bead by entering on the wide to pointed part of the bead. r) Repeat the process made on the second and third bead until the edge is reached before tying. s) To make the second variation, follow the above procedures but replace the second, fourth, sixth, eighth, and tenth Job's tears with wood beads. t) For the third variation, follow the procedures in embellishing but replace the wood beads with plastic beads.

Procedures in Making Valance Curtain

Using the following procedures, the operation time reduces in 7-9 minutes compared to existing procedures in sewing a valance curtain (Beck, 2021) because there was systematic material handling. The said systematic identified steps are: a) Cut 41 ½" x 12 ½" along the lengthwise grain b) Fold and sew each side of the fabric c) Hem the bottom d) Hem the top by leaving an inch for the curtain rod. e) On the wrong side, divide the length of the fabric into three equal parts and mark it 1. From the mark, measure 1" on each opposing direction. f) Fold on the outer marking and bring it to the center mark. Secure with pins. g) Sew permanently. h) Press the folds to make pleat. Do the same to the other 2 divisions i) Topstitch the top of the heading ¼" from the edge. j) To make the circular shaped embellishment, thread 6 white job's tears using nylon wire. k) Estimate 1 ¼" excess nylon wire from the tip of each last Job's tears. Insert the opposite end of nylon wire on the last Job's tears before pulling to make a circular shape. Tie each end of the nylon wire in between the Job's tears. Make 4. l) Attach the first circular shaped threaded Job's tears on the top left corner of the sewn fabric by hand sewing. Make sure that it will not go through the other side of the heading. Attach the next 2 circle shaped Job's tears on the heading part where the fold is located by hand sewing and the other 1 on the top right corner m) Attach jump rings on the circle-shaped threaded beads using pliers. n) Make the detachable embellishment o) In embellishing with pure Jobs tears, initially estimate the length of the nylon wire by placing the end of the nylon wire on the jump ring and the length of the nylon wire toward the next jump ring ensuring the desired curve is reached, return to the first jump ring. Add extra length of about 5". p) Then tie the nylon wire on the lobster hook with one nylon wire longer than the other and q) thread the nylon wire following the sequence 4 brown Job's tears, 1 small white Job's tears, 2 big white Job's tears, 1 small white Job's tears. Continue the sequence until the desired curve is reached. Tie the end of the nylon wire to the other lobster hook and thread the other nylon wire following the above sequence. but add 2-4 brown beads to make the second thread have a lower curve. r) In embellishing with Job's tears mixed with wood beads, follow the

above procedures in making detachable embellishment with pure beads by replacing the small white Job's tears with 6mm wood beads, 2 big white Job's tears with one 10 mm barrel wood beads and the other small white Job's tears with 6mm wood beads. s) In embellishing with Job's tears mixed with plastic beads, follow the above procedures in making detachable embellishment with pure beads by replacing the small wood beads with 6mm plastic beads, 10mm barrel wood beads with one 10 mm plastic beads and the other small wood beads with 6mm plastic beads.

Procedures in Making Throw Pillowcase

The following procedures resulted to reduced operation time by 10-13 minutes since material handling movements are systematic compared to existing assembling method (Mulvenna, 2020). The discovered effective procedures are: a) Measure 14"x14" of manila paper then cut. Lay it out on the wrong side of the fabric and pin. Trace the lines and add 1/2" seam allowance all around the sides before cutting; b) To make the envelope closure, measure 8" x 14" of manila paper and cut. Lay it on the wrong side of the fabric and pin. Add 1 1/2" on one side for the hem and 1/2" seam allowance on the remaining sides. Cut 2 pieces; c) Individually sew the 8"x14" cut fabric starting on the 1 1/2" seam allowance. Fold the sewing line and fold another 1/2" to make the hem. Do it to the other piece; d) Lay the 14"x14" fabric with the right side up; e) Put the 8"x14" fabric on top of the 14"x14" matching the construction lines (right sides together) lay also the other 8"x14" on the top corner and match the construction lines before pinning; f) Machine stitch the sewing lines; and g) Turn it inside out.

To make the embellishment with pure Job's tears, get nylon wire and estimate the length by placing the end of the nylon wire on one corner of the pillowcase moving it slowly to the other corner until it reaches the first corner. Estimate the length of the nylon wire needed by putting it in all the four sides of the throw pillowcase. Add extra 5" of nylon wire before cutting. Tie a knot on one end then thread six brown Job's tears, one medium size Job's tear, 2 large white Job's tears, and another medium size white Job's tears. Follow the sequence of threading the Job's tears until the whole nylon wire is full. Temporarily make a knot. Attach the sewn Job's tears on the edge of the pillow cover. Thread the needle twice. Insert the threaded needle on the wrong side corner of the pillow cover. Let it hold the knot of the Job's tears. Insert the needle towards the inside of the pillow cover and bring it out on the edge after two Job's tears. Insert needle again towards inside of the pillow cover before pulling. repeat process until the last corner is reached. To make the embellishment with mix Job's tears and wood beads, follow the same procedures except that the wood beads will be added.

The procedures identified were entirely original inclusive of structural and decorative designs. The shape structure and dimensions of the curtain tieback, valance curtain and pillowcase as well as the embellishments applied as decorative design were self-made ensuring the originality (Omran et al., 2025).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following were concluded:

1. Textile wastes from schools offering dressmaking or tailoring and dressmaking shops at Bokod, Benguet are used for rugs, pillow stuffing, or patches due to lack of time for repurposing or lack of manpower;
2. All repurposed variations of curtain tiebacks, valance curtains, and throw pillowcases are highly accepted due to harmonious color combinations, the integration of Job's tears showcases natural beauty and depicts the cultural heritage of Iballoys, and the price is affordable and competitive;
3. The age group under 18-24 favors a curtain tieback and a valance curtain decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads, and a throw pillowcase decorated with pure Job's tears, while the 25-44 age group prefers a curtain tieback, a valance curtain, and a throw pillowcase decorated with Job's tears mixed with wooden beads. Lastly, 45-65, prefers a curtain tieback, valance curtain, and throw pillowcase decorated with pure Job's tears.
4. Systematic materials handling movements result to an operation time reduction from 3 to 13 minutes.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The conduct of skills transfers on repurposing textile wastes generated from clothing laboratory shops or dressmaking shops may be conducted among interested individuals in the community to reduce textile wastes in the landfill and provide an alternative source of income. Further, a proper solid wastes disposal awareness campaign maybe conducted.
2. Advocate the use of Job's tears in repurposing to depict cultural meaning on designs and highlight ethnic identity, however, establishment of Job's tears plantation as a source of the material is recommended.
3. Commercialization of repurposed textiles made into home décor may be done considering the preferences of each age group.
4. Explore more systematic procedures in sewing home décor to suit the needs of PWDs or members of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps).

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher has adhered to the following considerations. The researcher asked permission to conduct the study to the Municipal Mayor, and the school heads of the participating schools. Before collecting data from participants, the researcher has also explained the objectives, purpose of the study, and that their participation is voluntary. An informed consent was obtained from the respondents. With respect to

data privacy, only the necessary information was collected and were deleted and disposed after the conduct of the study.

Different artificial intelligence (AI) tools or applications were used which includes Elicit and Scispace for the efficient search of relevant and current literature, Perplexity was used to provide the structure of the Literature review and background of the study, provide examples, and clarify complex concepts. Also, Scribber Citation Generator was used to generate the references in APA format. In connection to the use of these AI tools, the researcher carefully counter-checked and verified the outputs to make sure it is accurate.

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